

MODERN CONCEPTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE IN THE TEACHING OF EDUCATION SCIENCE IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article examines the modern concepts of development of environmental knowledge in the teaching of Education in elementary school students. The article analyzes the impact of environmental knowledge on students, the importance of modern educational methods, and approaches to the formation of environmental consciousness. Ways of more effective delivery of environmental knowledge will be studied with the help of modern pedagogical methods and technologies.

The article provides real examples of the successful use of various approaches and methods, analyzes the role of educational programs and pedagogical approaches in the formation of environmental awareness among students. Methods of increasing children's environmental knowledge through practical activities, interactive technologies, scientific projects and ecological projects are shown in detail.

The article also analyzes ways to increase the activity of elementary school students in the process of environmental education. Ways to improve the effectiveness of environmental education through the creation of modern concepts, pedagogical strategies and learning environments are considered.

As a result of the article, the importance of ecological knowledge and the role of modern concepts in the development of ecological consciousness among elementary school students is highlighted, and the importance of this process and its necessity for future generations is emphasized.

Keywords: environmental knowledge, elementary grades, science of education, modern concepts, environmental education, pedagogical approaches, students, environmental awareness, technologies, practical training, interactive technologies.

Introduction

The development of environmental knowledge in elementary school students is extremely important for several reasons:

Elementary age children absorb their knowledge quickly and effectively. By instilling environmental knowledge at this age, a conscious approach to nature, environment and environmental problems is formed in them.

Environmental awareness and sense of responsibility are brought up in children through ecological knowledge. They are aware of their responsibilities to preserve nature, save resources and protect the environment.

Environmental knowledge can be put into practice in the daily life of children. For example, developing habits such as separating waste, saving water, and using energy efficiently will help children become environmentally responsible people in the future.

By receiving environmental education from an early age, it is possible to cultivate a sense of respect for nature and living organisms in children. This, in turn, increases their desire to protect nature and not harm it.

Environmental knowledge helps children develop a deeper understanding of environmental problems and innovative approaches to solving them. This will serve as a key factor for effective solutions to environmental problems in the future.

The development of environmental knowledge among primary school students supports the principles of sustainable development. By choosing sustainable lifestyles, children contribute to creating a healthy and safe environment for future generations.

Ecological knowledge helps children understand the relationship between human activity and nature. This helps them to correctly assess and understand environmental conditions and their consequences. These reasons show how important it is to develop environmental knowledge in elementary school students. Through this, we prepare future generations as environmentally conscious and responsible people.

If the system of modern innovative approach to the process of ecological education is introduced, it is possible to achieve objectively necessary level of communication and mutual harmony between humanity and nature, environment and space. In our opinion, the program system of education inculcating humanistic ideas and the concept of living in harmony with nature, that man is a part of it, does not justify itself today. The emergence of misconceptions about natural resources, the dominance of the approach of an inexhaustible resource, and the fact that the desire to subjugate natural elements to man has not yet ended, which is the basis for breaking the ecological balance and destroying ecosystems, remains. In order to form the ecological consciousness of a person, it is necessary to completely restructure the views and ideas of a person, because the ecological norms that he has adopted become the norms of his behavior towards nature at the same time. Of course, this process encourages the use of the heritage of Central Asian thinkers in the formation of ecological thinking in elementary school students. This consciousness grows based on the logical processing of knowledge, serves as the basis for the transformation of knowledge into beliefs. However, the increase in the level of environmental education does not in itself lead to a higher environmental awareness, because the impulses arising from the acquired knowledge can be caused by personal negative qualities: passivity, indifference, irresponsibility, weakness. It is worth noting that studying the interaction of students with the environment and nature, their psychological aspects, solving environmental problems and developing new technologies, but not the behavior of students, it is necessary to pay attention to change. So to speak, it can be said that the ecological crisis is the result of a person's poor adaptation to the new reality. But before changing the views of young students on this issue, it is necessary to study its socio-psychological factors scientifically and practically. Solving this problem requires us to pay serious attention to the question of ecopsychology and ecological consciousness. The desire and ability to act responsibly in the environment requires teachers to pay attention to the formation of the student's personality, his needs and motivations. In turn, the formation of a student's personality is carried out on the basis of creating and strengthening a new worldview, strong faith, modern ideals, interests, inclinations, and a sense of inheritance of national values. These processes require that all activities are subordinated to consciousness on both sides.

The basic concept of ecology was created by Huxley in the last century; it is a biological science that describes the interactive processes of life and life beyond life and life and is based on a Darwinian perspective.

Child ecology is a branch of human ecology that studies how children interact with their environment in life, including their human relationships, particularly in terms of their growth and development.

In order to systematize children's ecology, sociobiology, cultural and medical anthropology, behavioral science, systems-information science, other new disciplines should be used in addition to the standard disciplines such as growth and development sciences, psychology, educational sciences and medical sciences. . as pediatrics, child health, microbiology, epidemiology, public health, hygiene and other clinical and basic medical sciences. In other words, children's ecology must be holistic and can be applied to all aspects of children's lives.

In order to distinguish and classify the children's ecosystem, I modified the Doxiadis-Lourie and Bronfenbrenner models into four ecosystems, namely micro-, mini-, meso- and macro-ecosystems (1-3).

A microecosystem is a space or world that a child can evaluate or understand through the sensory system and interactive processes with other people. This is the human network that immediately surrounds the child. In the case of the fetus, the microsystem is the mother's uterine cavity, while in infants it consists primarily of interactive personal relationships with parents, and later, of course, with siblings and other individuals. grandparents and extended family members.

A mini-ecosystem is a family, home and home as the basic unit of society and society. It includes not only software such as human relations and culture, but also technical tools such as housing structure and sanitation. Beyond the mini-ecosystem is the macroecosystem, which is society and society.

Between the macro-ecosystem and the mini-ecosystem, the meso-ecosystem acts as a connecting link, which includes kindergartens, kindergartens and schools, which are important for children. This system supports children's transition from family to community as they grow up.

If we could make a schematic plan of an ecosystem for children, it would be a concentric structure as shown in Figure 1.

(Figure 1) Concentric circle structure of the ecosystem for children.

As a microecosystem, the mother's body has an important influence on the fetus not only physico-chemically, but also culturally. As for the first, it is clear that intrauterine growth retardation is caused by maternal smoking and other factors. However, regarding the latter, I must emphasize that mothers can watch television for many hours a day, as in Japan, we

must take into account the effect of the mini-ecosystem on the fetus, because of the music and voices on the television. it can reach the fetus in the womb.

It is well known that babies imitate or imitate their behavior. If you slowly stick out your tongue in front of the child, he will move his lips and show the tip of the tongue, imitating the movement of your mouth (11, 22, 33).

The most amazing fact is that even a newborn baby can imitate or imitate and therefore this program is present at birth. This learning is the other side of the coin and may be the biological basis of learning in relation to other higher brain functions such as memorization, reasoning and belief.

A primitive walking or stepping reflex seems to be useful for understanding imitation and even learning programs. At birth, when the newborn baby is held with both hands and the feet can touch the hard board, the baby shows emergency movements. A newborn baby is considered to have a "walking" or "walking" program. This reflex disappears within 1 or 2 months, due to the lack of perception of three-dimensional space and the muscles of the lower extremities are insufficient to bear weight. If this program still continues to function, if the stepping reflex can appear in the months after birth, then it is considered that there is some abnormality in the baby's brain, and clinical and laboratory tests are used to identify the lesion. passes. But after about 12 months, a healthy baby can recognize objects in three dimensions and has enough muscle strength to support body weight. Then when the walking program is turned on again, they bend over and start walking.

After that, they start imitating and imitating the children or teachers around them in kindergarten or kindergarten and start running, jumping or even dancing. The walking program gets more information from the simulation and even learns to change itself

To find the biological basis of culture, the concept of sociobiology, introduced by Wilson and his group at Harvard University, gives us some idea. There is a connection between imitation programs and higher brain functions that have led to the creation of human culture and civilization.

They argue that only humans have real culture, that is, "euculture". While other animals have some sort of primitive culture, "urculture," most have no culture, "culture." Culture depends on the ability to imitate, learn, teach, and justify or represent what is thought through symbols, letters, etc. It should be noted that those who possess true culture are only those who, in addition to imitation, learning, and teaching, have a well-developed reasoning or representational faculty; that is, only human beings (24).

The five sense systems collect information from the ecosystems from birth or even the fetus and then connect the programs of the body and mind from within. A child also has programmed growth and development programmed by the body and mind. Energy for growth is provided as nutrition through the body's programs, particularly the digestive program. For development, especially mental, programs of consciousness, in particular, are provided as information by the emotional system. For these programs to run smoothly, children need to be well-educated along with good nutrition. If the programs of the mind and body are not well executed, the programs of growth and development are not well adjusted and such children do not develop, which is seen in sensory deprivation syndrome. Therefore, tenderness, love and humanity are important for them.

Children are surrounded by the ecosystem in everyday life, in other words, they live in the family, school and community. The intelligence program is especially affected by exogenous stimulation of ecosystems: micro-, mini-, meso- and macro-ecosystems, all of which provide such information. Each ecosystem interacts with the other at different levels and is influenced by natural, biological, physico-chemical and socio-cultural environmental factors. Among

them, human factors, that is, the element of human networks in the form of political and economic structures, is the most important, since these structural features represent important determinants of education, health and welfare systems. But analyzes must understand the interaction between factors, they must be interdisciplinary and based on the perspective of children's ecology.

Summary

Shows how important it is to develop environmental knowledge and use modern concepts in the education of primary school students. The importance of ecological education is to form a responsible approach to nature and the environment in children, to expand ecological awareness and knowledge. With the help of modern pedagogical methods and technologies, there is an opportunity to convey environmental knowledge more effectively. By considering the impact of environmental knowledge on students on the basis of examples and practices, it is determined that modern methods and technologies have a great role in the development of environmental education. This plays an important role in educating future generations as ecologically responsible and conscious people.

In general, the development of environmental knowledge and the use of modern concepts in elementary grades will help make the educational process interesting, effective and meaningful, and will make a significant contribution to environmental sustainability and nature protection in the future.

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